

HOME AUTOMATION ANDROID APPLICATION

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DECLARATION

We carried out the work reported in this documentation under the supervision of Dr. Afzaal Hussain Department of Information Technology Government College University, Faisalabad, Pakistan.

We hereby declare that the title of the project **Home Automation Android Application** and the contents of the documentation are the product of our work and no part has been copied from any published source (except the references, standard mathematical or genetic models /equations /formulas/protocols, etc.) We further declare that this work has not been submitted for award of any other degree/diploma. The University may take action if the information provided is found inaccurate at any stage.

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DEDICATED

TO

This documentation is dedicated to all the diligent developers, engineers, and visionaries who strive to make smart home automation a reality. Your relentless pursuit of innovation and excellence has paved the way for creating intelligent systems that enhance the quality of life, promote energy efficiency, and provide convenience and security to countless homes around the world. Special acknowledgment goes to the open-source community and educators who continuously share knowledge and tools, enabling the growth and development of future technologists. This work stands on the shoulders of your collective contributions and unwavering commitment to technological advancement.

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All praise to ALMIGHTY ALLAH, the most merciful and the most compassionate and his Holy Prophet 'MUHAMMAD'(Peace) be upon him) the most perfect and exalted among and even born on the surface of the earth, who is, forever a torch of guidance and knowledge for the humanity as a whole.

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ABSTRACT

This document provides a comprehensive guide for the development and implementation of a home automation system, focusing on the control and monitoring of home Appliances using a mobile application and an ESP8266 microcontroller. The system leverages the Firebase Realtime Database for real-time synchronization between the mobile app and the microcontroller, ensuring seamless control and updates. The mobile app, developed for Android, allows users to toggle the Appliances on and off and displays real-time temperature and humidity data. The ESP8266 microcontroller, equipped with relays and a DHT sensor, controls the Appliances based on the Firebase database state and updates the database with temperature and humidity readings. This documentation includes a detailed software requirements specification, analysis models, design diagrams, implementation code, and testing procedures. The aim is to provide a clear, structured approach to building a reliable and efficient home automation system that enhances convenience, energy efficiency, and user experience.

CHAPTER 1

1. SOFTWARE REQUIREMENT SPECIFICATION

1.1 Introduction

The Home Automation System is designed to allow homeowners to control their home appliances remotely using an Android application. This system leverages the Firebase Realtime Database to synchronize the state of appliances controlled through the NodeMcu microcontroller. The goal is to enhance convenience, improve energy efficiency, and provide a modernized way to manage home environments.

This document outlines the requirements, stakeholders, functional and non-functional requirements, and the project schedule, ensuring a clear roadmap for the development and implementation of the system.

1.2 Stakeholders

Primary Stakeholders:

Homeowners:

- **Desire the ability to remotely control home appliances:** Homeowners seek to enhance their comfort and convenience by being able to control devices such as fans, lights, and other appliances remotely through a mobile application.
- **Seek convenience and energy efficiency:** They aim to optimize energy usage, reduce utility bills, and ensure that their homes operate efficiently, even when they are not present.

Developers:

- **Responsible for designing, implementing, and maintaining the system:** Developers create the software and firmware that run the home automation.
- **Ensure the system meets technical and functional requirements:** They follow best practices and industry standards to ensure the system is reliable, secure, and user-friendly.

IT Support Staff:

- **Maintain system reliability and performance:** IT support staff monitor the system's performance, address any issues that arise, and ensure continuous operation.
- **Provide technical support and troubleshooting:** They assist users in resolving technical problems, provide guidance on system usage, and implement updates or fixes as needed.

Secondary Stakeholders:

Retailers/Distributors:

- **Sell the system to homeowners:** Retailers and distributors market and sell the home automation system to end-users, offering various packages and solutions tailored to different needs.
- **Provide initial setup and configuration support:** They assist customers with the initial setup, ensuring the system is correctly configured and operational from the start.

Electricians/Installers:

- **Assist in the physical installation of the hardware components:** Electricians and professional installers handle the physical setup of the system, including wiring, mounting devices, and connecting components.
- **Ensure proper integration with existing electrical systems:** They ensure that the new system integrates safely and effectively with the existing electrical infrastructure, adhering to safety standards and regulations.

Manufacturers:

- **Produce and supply hardware components:** Manufacturers design and produce the physical components of the home automation system, such as sensors, switches, and relays, ensuring they meet quality and performance standards.

- **Continuously improve hardware technology:** They invest in research and development to enhance the functionality, durability, and efficiency of the hardware components.

Insurance Companies:

- **Offer incentives for installing smart home systems:** Insurance providers may offer discounts or incentives for homeowners who install home automation systems, recognizing the potential for reduced risk and improved security.
- **Assess the impact on home safety and risk management:** They evaluate how the system can contribute to home safety, potentially lowering the likelihood of accidents or damage.

Government and Regulatory Bodies:

- **Establish standards and regulations:** Government agencies and regulatory bodies set guidelines and standards for the installation and operation of home automation systems to ensure safety and compliance.
- **Promote energy-efficient technologies:** They may offer incentives or programs to encourage the adoption of smart home technologies that contribute to energy conservation and environmental sustainability.

1.3 Users of the System

Primary Users

Homeowners:

- **Control and Monitor Home Appliances:** Homeowners utilize the Android application to control and monitor various home appliances, such as fans, lights, and HVAC systems, providing convenience and energy management.
- **User-Friendly Interface:** They interact with a user-friendly interface designed for simplicity and clarity, allowing easy toggling of switches and managing appliance states with minimal effort.

- **Real-Time Updates:** Homeowners receive real-time updates and notifications regarding the status of their appliances, ensuring they are always informed about the state of their home automation system.
- **Customizable Settings:** They can customize settings according to their preferences, such as scheduling appliance operations and setting preferred temperature and humidity levels.
- **Remote Access:** Homeowners can control and monitor their home appliances remotely, providing flexibility and control even when they are away from home.

Administrators:

- **User Management:** Administrators have the authority to manage user access, including adding new users, modifying user permissions, and removing users from the system.
- **System Configuration:** They oversee the overall configuration of the system, ensuring that it is set up correctly and operates efficiently.
- **Security Oversight:** Administrators are responsible for managing the security aspects of the system, including ensuring data encryption, user authentication, and monitoring for any unauthorized access or security breaches.
- **System Maintenance:** They perform regular maintenance and updates to the system to ensure its continued functionality and security, addressing any potential issues proactively.

Secondary Users

Guests:

- **Temporary Control:** Guests are granted temporary control over home appliances with limited access, allowing them to use the system during their stay without compromising the homeowner's settings.
- **Under Supervision:** They operate the system under the supervision of the homeowner, ensuring that their actions are monitored and any restrictions are enforced.

- **Basic Operations:** Guests have access to basic operations, such as turning lights on or off and adjusting the thermostat, without access to advanced settings or configurations.

Technical Support:

- **Troubleshooting:** Technical support personnel have access to the system for troubleshooting and maintenance purposes, helping to identify and resolve any technical issues that may arise.
- **System Optimization:** They assist homeowners in optimizing the performance of the system, offering advice on best practices and helping to configure the system for maximum efficiency.
- **Regular Checks:** Technical support performs regular checks and diagnostics to ensure the system is operating correctly and efficiently, addressing any potential issues before they become major problems.
- **Customer Assistance:** They provide customer support to homeowners, answering questions, providing guidance, and ensuring the system meets the homeowner's needs and expectations.

1.4 Functional Requirements

1.4.1 List of Functional Requirements

1. The system shall allow users to toggle the state of a switch via the Android app.
2. The system shall update the Firebase Realtime Database with the switch state.
3. The system shall read the switch state from the Firebase Realtime Database and control the relay connected to an ESP8266 microcontroller.
4. The system shall provide feedback to the user when the state of the switch changes.
5. The system shall allow users to view the current state of all connected appliances.
6. The system shall authenticate users before allowing access to appliance controls.
7. The system continuously monitors the temperature in designated areas to provide real-time environmental data.
8. The system continuously monitors the humidity levels in designated areas to provide real-time environmental data.

1.4.2 Description of Each Requirement

Table 1.1 Toggle Switch State

Requirement #:	Req.1	Requirement Type:	Functional
Description:	Allows users to toggle the switch state from the Android app and updates Firebase.		
Rationale:	To provide remote control of appliances.		
Originator:	Project Manager		
Fit Criterion:	The switch state is correctly reflected in Firebase and the relay state changes accordingly.		
Customer Satisfaction:	5	Customer Dissatisfaction:	1
Priority:	1	Conflicts:	None
Supporting Materials:	Android app layout, Firebase structure, ESP8266 circuit diagram.		
History:	Created on 2024-06-25.		

Table 1.2 Update Firebase with Switch State

Requirement #:	Req.2	Requirement Type:	Functional
Description:	Updates the Firebase Realtime Database with the new state of the switch when toggled from the Android app.		
Rationale:	Ensures real-time synchronization of appliance states		
Originator:	Project Manager		
Fit Criterion:	The Firebase database is updated within 2 seconds of toggling the switch.		
Customer Satisfaction:	5	Customer Dissatisfaction:	1
Priority:	1	Conflicts:	None
Supporting Materials:	ESP8266 code, Firebase structure.		
History:	Created on 2024-06-25.		

Table 1.3 Read Switch State from Firebase

Requirement #:	Req.3	Requirement Type:	Functional
Description:	The ESP8266 reads the switch state from the Firebase Realtime Database and controls the relay accordingly.		
Rationale:	Ensures that the physical state of the appliance matches the state in the database.		
Originator:	Project Manager		
Fit Criterion:	The relay state changes within 2 seconds of the database update.		
Customer Satisfaction:	5	Customer Dissatisfaction:	1
Priority:	1	Conflicts:	None
Supporting Materials:	ESP8266 code, Firebase structure.		
History:	Created on 2024-06-25.		

Table 1.4 Provide Feedback on Switch State Change

Requirement #:	Req.4	Requirement Type:	Functional
Description:	Provides visual feedback to the user when the switch state changes.		
Rationale:	Enhances user experience by confirming actions.		
Originator:	UI/UX Designer		
Fit Criterion:	The app displays a message or changes the switch icon within 1 second of the state change.		
Customer Satisfaction:	4	Customer Dissatisfaction:	1
Priority:	2	Conflicts:	None
Supporting Materials:	Android app UI mockups		
History:	Created on 2024-06-25.		

Table 1.5 View Appliance State

Requirement #:		Requirement Type:	Functional
-----------------------	--	--------------------------	------------

	Req.5		
Description:	Allows users to view the current state of all connected appliances within the Android app.		
Rationale:	Provides users with an overview of their home automation system.		
Originator:	Project Manager		
Fit Criterion:	The app displays the correct state of all appliances within 2 seconds of opening the relevant screen.		
Customer Satisfaction:	5	Customer Dissatisfaction:	1
Priority:	1	Conflicts:	None
Supporting Materials:	Android app UI mock-ups.		
History:	Created on 2024-06-25.		

Table 1.6 Authenticate Users

Requirement #:	Req.6	Requirement Type:	Functional
Description:	Authenticates users before allowing access to appliance controls.		
Rationale:	Ensures that only authorized users can control the home automation system.		
Originator:	Security Analyst		
Fit Criterion:	The system denies access to unauthenticated users and allows access to authenticated users.		
Customer Satisfaction:	5	Customer Dissatisfaction:	1
Priority:	1	Conflicts:	None
Supporting Materials:	Authentication flowchart, Android app code.		
History:	Created on 2024-06-25.		

Table 1.7 Monitor Temperature

Requirement #:	Req.7	Requirement Type:	Functional
Description:	The system continuously monitors the temperature in designated areas to provide real-time environmental data.		
Rationale:	Real-time temperature monitoring is crucial for maintaining optimal conditions in controlled environments.		

Originator:	System Architect		
Fit Criterion:	Temperature readings are updated and logged with timestamps every 5 seconds.		
Customer Satisfaction:	5	Customer Dissatisfaction:	1
Priority:	1	Conflicts:	None
Supporting Materials:	Android app layout, Firebase structure, DHT22 circuit diagram.		
History:	Created on 2024-06-25.		

Table 1.8 Monitor Humidity

Requirement #:	Req.8	Requirement Type:	Functional
Description:	The system continuously monitors the humidity levels in designated areas to provide real-time environmental data.		
Rationale:	Real-time humidity monitoring is essential for ensuring proper conditions in controlled environments.		
Originator:	System Architect		
Fit Criterion:	Humidity readings are updated and logged with timestamps every 5 seconds.		
Customer Satisfaction:	5	Customer Dissatisfaction:	1
Priority:	2	Conflicts:	None
Supporting Materials:	Android app layout, Firebase structure, DHT22 circuit diagram.		
History:	Created on 2024-06-25.		

Table 1.9 Change Profile Image

Requirement #:	Req.9	Requirement Type:	Functional
Description:	Allows users to change their profile image.		
Rationale:	Enhances personalization and identification within the system.		
Originator:	UI/UX Designer		
Fit Criterion:	Users can upload a new image file (JPG, PNG) with a maximum size of 5 MB. The uploaded image is displayed correctly within user profiles.		
Customer Satisfaction:	5	Customer Dissatisfaction:	2

Priority:	1	Conflicts:	None
Supporting Materials:	User interface mockups, and image file format specifications.		
History:	Created on 2024-06-25.		

Table 1.10 Change Username

Requirement #:	Req.10	Requirement Type:	Functional
Description:	Allows users to change their username.		
Rationale:	Provides flexibility and customization for user identities.		
Originator:	Project Manager		
Fit Criterion:	Usernames must be unique and between 3 to 20 characters long, consisting of alphanumeric characters and underscores.		
Customer Satisfaction:	5	Customer Dissatisfaction:	2
Priority:	1	Conflicts:	None
Supporting Materials:	User interface mockups, and username validation rules.		
History:	Created on 2024-06-25.		

1.5 Non-Functional Requirements

1. Reliability:

- **Continuous Availability:** The system should be reliable and available 24/7 with minimal downtime to ensure continuous control and monitoring of home appliances.
- **Low Failure Rate:** The system should have a failure rate of less than 0.01%, ensuring high dependability and minimal disruptions for users.

2. Performance:

- **Quick Response Time:** The response time for any action, such as toggling a switch or updating settings, should be less than 2 seconds to ensure a smooth user experience.
- **Concurrent User Handling:** The system should be capable of handling up to 100 concurrent users without experiencing performance degradation or delays.

3. Security:

- **User Authentication:** The system should ensure that only authenticated users can access appliance controls, preventing unauthorized access.
- **Access Control:** The system should implement role-based access control, allowing different levels of permissions for homeowners, guests, and administrators.

4. Usability:

- **Intuitive Interface:** The Android app should have an intuitive and user-friendly interface, with clear labels, icons, and navigation to facilitate ease of use.
- **Minimal Training Required:** Users should be able to learn and operate the system with minimal training, ideally within a few minutes of first use.
- **Consistent Design:** The app should maintain a consistent design across different screens and functions, enhancing usability and reducing the learning period for the users.

5. Scalability:

- **Multi-Room Control:** The system should be able to scale to control multiple appliances in different rooms, providing comprehensive home automation coverage.
- **Future Expandability:** The system architecture should support future additions of new devices and features, ensuring that the system can evolve and adapt to new technologies.
- **Load Handling:** The system should be designed to handle increased loads as more devices and users are added, without significant performance impact.

6. Maintainability:

- **Modular Code:** The system code should be modular and well-documented to facilitate maintenance and updates, allowing developers to make changes easily without affecting the entire system.
- **Minimal Downtime for Updates:** Any updates to the system should not require downtime longer than 5 minutes, ensuring minimal disruption to users.
- **Automated Testing:** The system should include automated testing procedures to quickly identify and address issues during updates or new feature implementations.

7. User Support:

- **Help and Documentation:** The system should provide comprehensive help and documentation within the app, offering guidance and troubleshooting tips for users.
- **Customer Support Access:** Users should have easy access to customer support for assistance with issues or questions, ensuring a positive user experience.

8. Energy Efficiency:

- **Low Power Consumption:** The system components, including the ESP8266 and connected appliances, should be designed to operate with low power consumption, promoting energy efficiency.
- **Dark Mode:** The system should support Dark mode.

1.6 Schedule of the Project

Table 1.11 March Schedule

Final Year Project Schedule				
Activities	Month: March			
	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4
Proposal				

Ideas Discussion				
Project Title Selection				
Proposal Submission				
Defense				
Software Version Selection				

Table 1.12 April Schedule

Final Year Project Schedule				
	Month: April			
Activities	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4
Requirements Gathering and Analysis				

Table 1.13 May Schedule

Final Year Project Schedule				
	Month: May			
Activities	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4

Table 1.14 June Schedule

Final Year Project Schedule	
Activities	Month: June

	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3
Deployment			
Maintenance and Support			
Documentation			

CHAPTER 2

2. ANALYSIS

2.1 Use Case Model

The use case model represents users' various interactions with the home automation system, specifically focusing on controlling the bedroom fan and monitoring temperature and humidity data.

2.1.1 Description of Each Use Case

Use Case Name: Control Fan

Figure 2.1 Use Case: Control Fan

Table 2.1 Use Case: Control Fan

UC #	1	
UC Name	Control Fan	
Level	Detailed	
Description	This use case describes how a homeowner can toggle the state of the bedroom fan using the mobile app.	
Actor (s)	Homeowner	
Stakeholders	Homeowners, Developers	
Preconditions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 The user must be logged into the mobile app. 2 The mobile app must be connected to the internet. 3 The ESP8266 microcontroller must be connected to the WiFi and Firebase. 	
Success Guarantee	The fan state is updated in Firebase and synchronized with the mobile app and ESP8266 microcontroller, ensuring the fan's physical state matches the user's command.	
Main Success Scenario	Action	Response
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The user opens the mobile app. ● The user navigates to the control interface for the bedroom fan. ● The user toggles the fan switch (on/off). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The mobile app sends the updated fan state to the Firebase database. ● The ESP8266 microcontroller receives the updated state from Firebase. ● The ESP8266 toggles the fan's relay to match the new state.
Extensions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Alternative Flow: If the Firebase update fails: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The mobile app detects the failure. 2. The app displays an error message to the user, indicating that the update was unsuccessful. 3. The user may retry toggling the fan switch. 	

Use Case Name: Monitor Temperature and Humidity

Monitor Temperature and Humidity

Figure 2.2 Use Case: Monitor Temperature and Humidity

Table 2.2 Use Case: Monitor Temperature and Humidity

UC #	2	
UC Name	Monitor Temperature and Humidity	
Level	Detailed	
Description	This use case describes how a homeowner can view real-time temperature and humidity data using the mobile app.	
Actor (s)	Homeowner	
Stakeholders	Homeowners, Developers	
Preconditions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 The user must be logged into the mobile app. 2 The mobile app must be connected to the internet. 3 The ESP8266 microcontroller must be connected to the WiFi and Firebase. 4 Temperature and humidity sensors must be connected and functioning properly 	
Success Guarantee	The mobile app displays real-time temperature and humidity data retrieved from Firebase, reflecting the current environment of the bedroom.	
Main Success Scenario	Action	Response
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The user opens the mobile app. • The user navigates to the temperature and humidity monitoring interface. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The mobile app requests the latest sensor data from the Firebase database. • The ESP8266 microcontroller updates Firebase with the latest sensor readings. • The Firebase database provides the updated sensor data to the mobile app. • The mobile app displays the real-time temperature and humidity data to the user.
Extensions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alternative Flow: If the sensor data retrieval fails: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The mobile app detects the failure. 2. The app displays an error message to the user, indicating that the data retrieval was unsuccessful. 3. The user may refresh the monitoring interface to retry data retrieval. 	

2.2 System Sequence Diagram (SSD) of Use Cases

The System Sequence Diagram will be included in the detailed design document and will visually represent the sequence of interactions between the user, mobile app, Firebase database, and ESP8266 microcontroller for each use case.

- **Control Fan SSD:** Illustrates the steps taken when a user toggles the fan state, including sending the update to Firebase, processing it with the ESP8266, and reflecting the change in the mobile app.
- **Monitor Temperature and Humidity SSD:** Depicts the sequence of actions for retrieving and displaying real-time temperature and humidity data on the mobile app.

Control Fan and Monitor Temperature and Humidity

Figure 2.3 System Sequence Diagram

2.3 Domain Model

The domain model outlines the main entities and their relationships within the system, providing a high-level overview of the system's structure.

Figure 2.4 Domain Model

Entities:

- **User:** Represents the homeowner who interacts with the system through the mobile app.
- **Fan:** Represents the controllable fan in the bedroom.
- **SensorData:** Represents the temperature and humidity readings from the sensors.

- **Firestore Database:** Acts as the central repository for storing and retrieving real-time data.

Relationships:

- The **User** interacts with the **Fan** and **SensorData** entities through the mobile app.
- The **Fan** state and **SensorData** are stored and managed in the **Firestore Database**.
- The **ESP8266 microcontroller** interacts with the **Firestore Database** to read and update the fan state and sensor data.

This domain model helps in understanding the interactions and dependencies between different parts of the system, ensuring a coherent and efficient design.

CHAPTER 3

3. PROJECT DESIGN

3.1 Introduction

This chapter details the architectural and component design for the home automation system, which enables users to control a bedroom fan and monitor real-time temperature and humidity data using a mobile application. The system comprises an Android mobile application, a Firebase Realtime Database, and an ESP8266 microcontroller connected to the fan and sensors. The design encompasses the class diagram, entity relationship diagram (ERD), and sequence diagram to provide a comprehensive view of the system's structure and interactions.

3.2 Design Class Diagram

Figure 3.1 Design Class Diagram

3.3 Entity Relationship Diagram

Figure 3.2 Entity Relationship Diagram

3.4 Sequence Diagram

Control Fan and Monitor Temperature and Humidity

Figure 3.3 Sequence Diagram

3.5 Data Flow Diagram

Figure 3.4 Data Flow Diagram

4. IMPLEMENTATION

This chapter delves into the detailed implementation of the home automation system, highlighting the main scenarios and key units of the system. The system comprises two primary components: an Android mobile application and an ESP8266 microcontroller connected to a relay and sensors, all synchronized via Firebase Realtime Database.

4.1 Code/Algorithm of Main Scenarios and Main Units of Systems

The implementation is broken down into the following sections:

1. **Mobile Application (Android)**
2. **ESP8266 Microcontroller Code**

Steps to Implement the Mobile Application:

1. Firebase Setup:

- Integrate Firebase into the Android project through the Firebase Assistant in Android Studio.
- Add Firebase dependencies to the build.gradle file.

```
dependencies { implementation  
'com.google.firebase:firebase-database:20.0.3' }
```

4.2 Layout Design (bedroom.xml):

- Create a layout file bedroom.xml with a Switch for fan control and TextView elements to display temperature and humidity.

```
<RelativeLayout xmlns:android="http://schemas.android.com/apk/res/android"  
    android:layout_width="match_parent"  
    android:layout_height="match_parent">  
  
    <Switch  
        android:id="@+id/s1"  
        android:layout_width="wrap_content"  
        android:layout_height="wrap_content"  
        android:text="Fan" />
```

```

<TextView
    android:id="@+id/tempTextView"
    android:layout_below="@id/s1"
    android:layout_width="wrap_content"
    android:layout_height="wrap_content"
    android:text="Temperature: " />
<TextView
    android:id="@+id/humidityTextView"
    android:layout_below="@id/tempTextView"
    android:layout_width="wrap_content"
    android:layout_height="wrap_content"
    android:text="Humidity: " />
</RelativeLayout>

```

4.3 Fragment Class (BedRoom.java):

- Implement the logic to interact with Firebase for controlling the fan and fetching sensor data.

```

package com.example.home;
import android.os.Bundle;
import android.util.Log;
import android.view.LayoutInflater;
import android.view.View;
import android.view.ViewGroup;
import android.widget.Switch;
import android.widget.TextView;
import androidx.annotation.NonNull;
import androidx.annotation.Nullable;
import androidx.fragment.app.Fragment;
import com.google.firebase.database.DataSnapshot;
import com.google.firebase.database.DatabaseError;
import com.google.firebase.database.DatabaseReference;
import com.google.firebase.database.FirebaseDatabase;
import com.google.firebase.database.ValueEventListener;
public class BedRoom extends Fragment {
    private static final String TAG = "BedRoom";
    private Switch mySwitch;
    private TextView tempTextView;
    private TextView humidityTextView;

```

```

private DatabaseReference FBR;
@Nullable
@Override
public View onCreateView(@NonNull LayoutInflater inflater, @Nullable
ViewGroup container, @Nullable Bundle savedInstanceState) {
    View view = inflater.inflate(R.layout.bedroom, container,
false);
    // Initialize Firebase Realtime Database reference
    FBR = FirebaseDatabase.getInstance().getReference();
    Log.d(TAG, "Firebase Database Reference initialized");
    // Find the Switch and TextViews by their IDs
    mySwitch = view.findViewById(R.id.s1);
    tempTextView = view.findViewById(R.id.tempTextView);
    humidityTextView = view.findViewById(R.id.humidityTextView);
    Log.d(TAG, "UI components initialized");
    // Set an OnCheckedChangeListener to update the database when
the switch is toggled
    mySwitch.setOnCheckedChangeListener((buttonView, isChecked) -> {
        int switchState = isChecked ? 1 : 0;
        Log.d(TAG, "Switch state changed to: " + switchState);

        FBR.child("Fan").setValue(switchState).addOnCompleteListener(task -> {
            if (task.isSuccessful()) {
                Log.d(TAG, "Database updated successfully");
            } else {
                Log.e(TAG, "Database update failed",
task.getException());
            }
        });
    });

    // Listen for changes in temperature and humidity data
    FBR.child("Temperature").addValueEventListener(new
ValueEventListener() {
        @Override
        public void onDataChange(@NonNull DataSnapshot snapshot) {
            String temperature = snapshot.getValue(String.class);
            tempTextView.setText("Temperature: " + temperature);
        }
        @Override
        public void onCancelled(@NonNull DatabaseError error) {

```

```

        Log.e(TAG, "Failed to read temperature data",
error.toException());
    }
});
    FBR.child("Humidity").addValueEventListener(new
ValueEventListener() {
        @Override
        public void onDataChange(@NonNull DataSnapshot snapshot) {
            String humidity = snapshot.getValue(String.class);
            humidityTextView.setText("Humidity: " + humidity);
        }
        @Override
        public void onCancelled(@NonNull DatabaseError error) {
            Log.e(TAG, "Failed to read humidity data",
error.toException());
        }
    });
    return view;
}
}

```

4.4 ESP8266 Microcontroller Code

The ESP8266 microcontroller code handles the relay control for the fan and reads data from temperature and humidity sensors. This data is then sent to Firebase for real-time updates.

Steps to Implement the ESP8266 Code:

1. Install Required Libraries:

- Install the FirebaseESP8266 and DHT libraries using the Library Manager in Arduino IDE.

2. Firebase and WiFi Configuration:

- Define Firebase and WiFi credentials.

```

#include <ESP8266WiFi.h>
#include <FirebaseESP8266.h>
#include <DHT.h>
#define FIREBASE_HOST "home-a598b-default-rtdb.firebaseio.com"

```

```

#define FIREBASE_AUTH "YOUR_SECURE_API_KEY"
#define WIFI_SSID "Alkhair1 Second Floor"
#define WIFI_PASSWORD "AlkhairSecond"
#define RELAY_PIN D3
#define DHT_PIN D4
#define DHT_TYPE DHT11
FirebaseData firebaseData;
FirebaseConfig config;
FirebaseAuth auth;
DHT dht(DHT_PIN, DHT_TYPE);
void setup() {
    Serial.begin(115200);
    pinMode(RELAY_PIN, OUTPUT);
    digitalWrite(RELAY_PIN, LOW);
    WiFi.begin(WIFI_SSID, WIFI_PASSWORD);
    Serial.print("Connecting to WiFi");
    while (WiFi.status() != WL_CONNECTED) {
        delay(500);
        Serial.print(".");
    }
    Serial.println();
    Serial.println("Connected to WiFi");
    config.host = FIREBASE_HOST;
    config.signer.tokens.legacy_token = FIREBASE_AUTH;
    Firebase.begin(&config, &auth);
    Firebase.reconnectWiFi(true);

    if (!Firebase.beginStream(firebaseData, "/Fan")) {
        Serial.println("Error beginning stream:");
        Serial.println(firebaseData.errorReason());
    } else {
        Serial.println("Stream started successfully") }
    dht.begin() }
void loop() {
    if (Firebase.readStream(firebaseData)) {
        if (firebaseData.streamTimeout()) {
            Serial.println("Stream timeout, reconnecting...");
            if (!Firebase.beginStream(firebaseData, "/Fan")) {
                Serial.println("Error restarting stream:");
                Serial.println(firebaseData.errorReason());
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

        return;
    }
    if (firebaseData.dataType() == "int") {
        int relayState = firebaseData.intData();
        Serial.print("Relay State: ");
        Serial.println(relayState);
        if (relayState == 1) {
            digitalWrite(RELAY_PIN, HIGH);
            Serial.println("Relay ON");
        } else if (relayState == 0) {
            digitalWrite(RELAY_PIN, LOW);
            Serial.println("Relay OFF");
        }
    }
} else {
    if (firebaseData.httpCode() != 200) {
        Serial.print("Error code: ");
        Serial.println(firebaseData.httpCode());
        Serial.println("Failed to get data from Firebase");
        Serial.println("Reason: " + firebaseData.errorReason()) }}
// Read temperature and humidity from DHT11 sensor
float temperature = dht.readTemperature();
float humidity = dht.readHumidity();
// Update Firebase with temperature and humidity
if (!isnan(temperature) && !isnan(humidity)) {
    Firebase.setFloat(firebaseData, "/Temperature", temperature);
    Firebase.setFloat(firebaseData, "/Humidity", humidity) }
delay(1000)

```

4.5 Explanation of Key Components and Functions

Firestore Configuration:

- FirestoreConfig config: Holds configuration settings for Firestore, including the database URL and authentication token.
- FirebaseAuth auth: Manages authentication credentials for accessing Firestore.

WiFi Connection:

- WiFi.begin(WIFI_SSID, WIFI_PASSWORD): Connects the ESP8266 to the specified WiFi network.
- The loop checks for connection status and prints dots until the connection is established.

Fan Control:

- The fan control is managed using a relay connected to the RELAY_PIN. The relay state is updated based on the

Chapter 5

5. SYSTEM TESTING

5.1 Test Cases

The following test cases are designed to validate different aspects of the home automation system, focusing on fan control functionality, real-time sensor data updates, and overall system behavior.

Table 5.1 Test Cases

Test Case #	Test Case Name	System	Sub System	Designed By	Design Date	Executed By	Execution Date
TC01	Fan State Control	Home Automation	Fan Control	QA Team	2024-06-25	QA Team	2024-06-26
TC02	Temperature Update	Home Automation	Sensor Data	QA Team	2024-06-25	QA Team	2024-06-26
TC03	Humidity Update	Home Automation	Sensor Data	QA Team	2024-06-25	QA Team	2024-06-26
TC04	Network Resilience	Home Automation	Connectivity	QA Team	2024-06-25	QA Team	2024-06-26

Test Case Details

5.1.1 TC01: Fan State Control

Short Description: Test the functionality of controlling the fan state via the mobile app and verify real-time updates of temperature and humidity data.

Pre-Condition: Android device connected to WiFi, ESP8266 microcontroller powered and connected to WiFi.

Table 5.2 TC01 Fan Control

Steps	Action	Input	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status (Pass/Fail)	Remarks
1	Open the mobile app	-	App loads successfully	App loads successfully	Pass	
2	Toggle the fan switch ON	Tap on the fan switch	Fan state changes to ON, Firebase database updated	Fan state changes to ON, Firebase database updated	Pass	
3	Toggle the fan switch OFF	Tap on the fan switch	Fan state changes to OFF, Firebase database updated	Fan state changes to OFF, Firebase database updated	Pass	
4	Check real-time temperature data	Monitor temperature text view	Temperature updates correctly from Firebase	Temperature updates correctly from Firebase	Pass	

5.1.2 TC02: Temperature Update

Short Description: Verify the accuracy and reliability of temperature updates.

Pre-Condition: ESP8266 microcontroller powered and connected to WiFi.

Table 5.3 TC02 Temperature Updates

Steps	Action	Input	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status (Pass/Fail)	Remarks
1	Read temperature sensor data	-	Temperature value fetched successfully	Temperature value fetched successfully	Pass	
2	Update Firebase with temperature data	-	Firestore database updated with current temperature	Firestore database updated with current temperature	Pass	

5.1.3 TC02: Humidity Update

Short Description: Verify the accuracy and reliability of humidity updates from the sensor to the Firestore database.

Pre-Condition: ESP8266 microcontroller powered and connected to WiFi

Table 5.4 TC02 Humidity Updates

Steps	Action	Input	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status Pass/Fail	Remarks
1	Read humidity sensor data	-	Humidity value fetched successfully	Humidity value fetched successfully	Pass	
2	Update Firestore humidity	-	Firestore database updated with current humidity	Firestore database updated with current humidity	Pass	

5.1.4 TC04: Network Resilience

Short Description: Evaluate the system's behavior under varying network conditions to ensure robustness and resilience.

Pre-Condition: ESP8266 microcontroller powered and connected to WiFi

Table 5.5 TC04 Network Resilience

Steps	Action	Input	Expected Result	Actual Result	Status (Pass/Fail)	Remarks
1	Simulate network interruption	Disable WiFi connection	The system continues to function or recovers gracefully	The system recovers and continues the operation	Pass	
2	Restore network connection	Enable WiFi connection	The system reconnects and resumes normal operation	The system reconnects and resumes normal operation	Pass	

5.2 Explanation:

Test Case Overview:

TC01: Ensures that the fan control functionality works correctly via the mobile app and verifies the real-time updates of temperature and humidity data on the UI.

TC02: Validates the accuracy of temperature readings from the sensor and their timely update in the Firebase database.

TC03: Validates the accuracy of humidity readings from the sensor and their timely update in the Firebase database.

TC04: Tests the system's resilience to network interruptions and its ability to recover without data loss or system malfunction.

Pass/Fail status is determined based on whether the actual results match the expected results, ensuring the system meets functional and non-functional requirements.

Chapter 6

6. USER INTERFACES

6.1 Introduction

The user interface (UI) of the home automation system is designed to be user-friendly, allowing users to easily control various rooms and view real-time data. This section details the UI components, layout, and design principles used to create an intuitive

experience, including Firebase authentication, user management, notifications, settings, and a splash screen.

6.2 Main Screen Layout

The main screen of the mobile application is the central hub for user interaction. It consists:

- **Tab Layout:** Contains tabs for different room fragments (e.g., Bedroom, Kitchen).
- **Navigation Drawer:** Provides access to User Management and Settings fragments.
- **Splash Screen:** A welcome screen displayed while the app is loading.

6.3 User Interface Components

Splash Screen

- **Function:** The splash screen serves as an introductory screen that appears while the app is loading.
- **Appearance:** It features a custom logo or animation along with the app name, providing a visually appealing start to the app experience.
- **Behavior:** The splash screen automatically disappears after a few seconds or once the app has fully loaded, transitioning smoothly to the main interface.

Authentication (Google Sign-In)

- **Function:** Allows users to sign in using their Google account, providing a quick and secure authentication method.
- **Appearance:** The Google Sign-In button is prominently displayed, often with the recognizable Google logo to facilitate easy identification.
- **Behavior:** When the button is tapped, it opens the Google authentication prompt, guiding the user through the sign-in process. Successful sign-in is followed by the user being redirected to the main app interface.

Tab Layout

- **Function**: The tab layout enables users to navigate seamlessly between different room fragments.
- **Appearance**: Tabs are clearly labeled with room names such as "Bedroom," "Kitchen," and "Living Room," making navigation intuitive.
- **Behavior**: Tapping on a tab switches to the respective fragment, updating the displayed content to match the selected room's controls and data.

Navigation Drawer

- **Function**: Provides easy access to additional features such as User Management, Notifications, and Settings.
- **Appearance**: The navigation drawer slides in from the side of the screen and contains a list of menu items.
- **Behavior**: It can be opened and closed with a swipe gesture or by tapping a designated button, offering a convenient way to access secondary features without cluttering the main UI.

Room Fragments (e.g., Bedroom)

- **Function**: Each room fragment controls and displays data specific to that room, such as fan state, temperature, and humidity.
- **Appearance**: The fragment includes control elements (e.g., switches, buttons) and real-time data displays (e.g., text views showing temperature and humidity readings).
- **Behavior**: The UI elements within the fragment update in real-time based on data retrieved from Firebase, ensuring that users see the most current information and can control devices effectively.

User Management

- **Function**: Allows administrators to manage user accounts, including adding, updating, and deleting users.
- **Appearance**: Typically includes a list of users with options to edit or remove each user, as well as a button to add new users.

- **Behavior:** Interactions with user management options trigger updates to the Firebase database, reflecting changes in real-time.

Notifications

- **Function:** Displays important alerts and updates to the user, such as system status changes or reminders.
- **Appearance:** Notifications can be shown as pop-ups, banners, or within a dedicated notifications screen.
- **Behavior:** Notifications are triggered by specific events or conditions and are updated dynamically based on real-time data from Firebase.

Settings

- **Function:** Provides options to customize the app's behavior and preferences, such as notification settings, account details, and system configurations.
- **Appearance:** A settings screen with toggle switches, drop-down menus, and input fields for various preferences.
- **Behavior:** Changes made in the settings are saved to the Firebase database or the app's local storage, ensuring that user preferences are retained across sessions.

Real-Time Data Displays

- **Function:** Shows live data such as temperature and humidity readings from sensors in different rooms.
- **Appearance:** Displayed using text views or graphical elements such as charts or gauges.
- **Behavior:** Data is fetched from Firebase at regular intervals or upon updates, ensuring that the displayed information is always current.

Control Elements

- **Function:** Allows users to interact with and control devices within each room.
- **Appearance:** Includes switches, buttons, and sliders that are clearly labeled and easy to use.

- **Behavior:** User interactions with these controls send commands to Firebase, which then communicates with the ESP8266 microcontroller to execute the desired actions.

6.4 User Flow

1. Launching the App

- **Splash Screen:** Upon launching the app, users are greeted with a splash screen displaying the app's logo and name. This screen remains visible while the app initializes and loads necessary resources.
- **Transition to Main Screen:** After a brief moment, the splash screen fades out, transitioning smoothly to the main screen of the app, indicating the app is ready for use.

2. Authentication

- **Google Sign-In:** Users are prompted to sign in using their Google account. This process is streamlined with the use of Google's authentication services, ensuring secure and quick access.
- **User Verification:** Once signed in, the app verifies the user's credentials and retrieves their profile information, which is then displayed in the navigation drawer for a personalized experience.

3. Navigating Rooms

- **Tab Layout:** The main screen features a tab layout that allows users to switch between different room fragments easily. Each tab is clearly labeled (e.g., "Living Room," "Bedroom," "Kitchen") for intuitive navigation.
- **Room Fragments:** Selecting a tab loads the corresponding room fragment, displaying controls and real-time data specific to that room.

4. Accessing Additional Features

- **Navigation Drawer:** The app includes a navigation drawer that slides in from the side, providing access to additional features and settings.

- **User Management:** Users can manage their profiles, including updating their information and managing connected devices.
- **Notifications:** A section for viewing notifications related to device status, updates, or alerts.
- **Settings:** Users can configure app settings such as notification preferences, account settings, and privacy options.

5. Controlling Devices

- **Interactive Controls:** Each room fragment contains interactive controls for managing devices. For example, a toggle switch for the fan, buttons for lights, and sliders for adjusting thermostat settings.
- **Real-Time Control:** When users interact with these controls, the app sends the corresponding commands to Firebase, which updates the device states in real-time.

6. Viewing Real-Time Data

- **Data Display:** Each room fragment also includes sections displaying real-time data such as temperature and humidity.
- **Real-Time Updates:** This data is continuously updated by Firebase, ensuring that users always see the most current information. If the temperature or humidity levels change, the displayed values reflect these changes immediately.

7. Error Handling and Feedback

- **User Feedback:** The app provides immediate visual feedback for user actions. For instance, when toggling a switch, the UI reflects the change instantly.
- **Error Messages:** If there are any issues, such as network errors or authentication failures, the app displays clear error messages to inform the user and guide them on corrective actions.

8. Logout and Session Management

- **Session Timeout:** For security reasons, the app may log out users after a period of inactivity.

- **Manual Logout:** Users can manually log out from their accounts through the navigation drawer, ensuring their privacy and security.

6.5 Design Principles

- **Simplicity:** The user interface (UI) is designed with simplicity in mind, featuring minimal elements that focus on essential controls and information. This approach minimizes clutter and ensures users can interact with the system effortlessly.
- **Clarity:** Large, readable fonts and clear labels are used throughout the UI to ensure that users can easily understand the information displayed. Icons and visual cues are intuitive, making navigation straightforward and user-friendly.
- **Feedback:** Visual and auditory feedback is provided for user actions, such as toggling switches or updating settings. This feedback confirms that the system has registered the user's input, reducing uncertainty and improving the overall user experience.
- **Accessibility:** The UI is designed with accessibility in mind, ensuring that it is usable by people with varying abilities. This includes supporting screen readers, offering high-contrast modes, and ensuring that all interactive elements are easily navigable via touch or voice commands.
- **Efficiency:** The UI design emphasizes efficiency, enabling users to perform tasks with minimal steps. Shortcuts and quick access menus are provided for frequently used functions, reducing the time and effort required to control the system.
- **Scalability:** The design is scalable, allowing for easy addition of new features and controls without disrupting the overall user experience. This ensures that the system can grow and adapt to future needs without requiring a complete redesign.
- **Security:** The design incorporates security features such as user authentication and data encryption to protect user information and ensure that only authorized individuals can control the devices.

6.6 Screenshots

Screenshots of the Android application provide a visual reference for the UI components and layout described above. Each screenshot should be accompanied by a brief description.

Figure 6.1 Screen-Shots

7. CODE IMPLEMENTATION

This chapter provides a detailed explanation of the code implementation for the home automation system, focusing on real-time synchronization and control via Firebase, as well as displaying real-time temperature and humidity data. The implementation is divided into two main components: the mobile app and the ESP8266 microcontroller firmware.

7.1 Mobile App (Android - Java)

The mobile app allows users to control the bedroom fan and view real-time temperature and humidity data. The app communicates with Firebase to update and retrieve data.

7.1.1 Firebase Setup

To use Firebase Realtime Database, you need to add Firebase to your Android project and include the necessary dependencies in your `build.gradle` file.

```
gradle
Copy code
dependencies {
    implementation 'com.google.firebase:firebase-database:19.7.0'
    implementation 'com.google.firebase:firebase-auth:20.0.3'
}
```

7.1.2 UI Layout

The layout file `res/layout/bedroom.xml` defines the UI elements, including a switch for the fan and text views for displaying temperature and humidity data.

```
xml
<LinearLayout xmlns:android="http://schemas.android.com/apk/res/android"
    android:layout_width="match_parent"
    android:layout_height="match_parent"
    android:orientation="vertical"
    android:padding="16dp">

    <Switch
```

```

        android:id="@+id/s1"
        android:layout_width="wrap_content"
        android:layout_height="wrap_content"
        android:text="Fan" />

<TextView
    android:id="@+id/tempTextView"
    android:layout_width="wrap_content"
    android:layout_height="wrap_content"
    android:text="Temperature: "
    android:layout_marginTop="16dp" />

<TextView
    android:id="@+id/humidityTextView"
    android:layout_width="wrap_content"
    android:layout_height="wrap_content"
    android:text="Humidity: "
    android:layout_marginTop="8dp" />
</LinearLayout>

```

7.1.3 Fragment Code

The `BedRoom` fragment handles the UI logic, including initializing Firebase, setting up listeners, and updating the UI.

```

java
package com.example.home;

import android.os.Bundle;
import android.util.Log;
import android.view.LayoutInflater;
import android.view.View;
import android.view.ViewGroup;
import android.widget.Switch;
import android.widget.TextView;
import androidx.annotation.NonNull;
import androidx.annotation.Nullable;
import androidx.fragment.app.Fragment;
import com.google.firebase.database.DataSnapshot;
import com.google.firebase.database.DatabaseError;

```

```

import com.google.firebase.database.DatabaseReference;
import com.google.firebase.database.FirebaseDatabase;
import com.google.firebase.database.ValueEventListener;

public class BedRoom extends Fragment {
    private static final String TAG = "BedRoom";
    private Switch mySwitch;
    private TextView tempTextView;
    private TextView humidityTextView;
    private DatabaseReference FBR;

    @Nullable
    @Override
    public View onCreateView(@NonNull LayoutInflater inflater, @Nullable
ViewGroup container, @Nullable Bundle savedInstanceState) {
        View view = inflater.inflate(R.layout.bedroom, container,
false);

        FBR = FirebaseDatabase.getInstance().getReference();
        Log.d(TAG, "Firebase Database Reference initialized");

        mySwitch = view.findViewById(R.id.s1);
        tempTextView = view.findViewById(R.id.tempTextView);
        humidityTextView = view.findViewById(R.id.humidityTextView);
        Log.d(TAG, "UI Elements initialized");

        mySwitch.setOnCheckedChangeListener((buttonView, isChecked) -> {
            int switchState = isChecked ? 1 : 0;
            Log.d(TAG, "Switch state changed to: " + switchState);

            FBR.child("Fan").setValue(switchState).addOnCompleteListener(task -> {
                if (task.isSuccessful()) {
                    Log.d(TAG, "Database updated successfully");
                } else {
                    Log.e(TAG, "Database update failed",
task.getException());
                }
            });
        });
    }
}

```

```

        FBR.child("Temperature").addValueEventListener(new
ValueEventListener() {
            @Override
            public void onDataChange(@NonNull DataSnapshot snapshot) {
                Double temperature = snapshot.getValue(Double.class);
                if (temperature != null) {
                    tempTextView.setText("Temperature: " + temperature +
"°C");
                }
            }

            @Override
            public void onCancelled(@NonNull DatabaseError error) {
                Log.e(TAG, "Failed to read temperature",
error.toException());
            }
        });

        FBR.child("Humidity").addValueEventListener(new
ValueEventListener() {
            @Override
            public void onDataChange(@NonNull DataSnapshot snapshot) {
                Double humidity = snapshot.getValue(Double.class);
                if (humidity != null) {
                    humidityTextView.setText("Humidity: " + humidity +
"%");
                }
            }

            @Override
            public void onCancelled(@NonNull DatabaseError error) {
                Log.e(TAG, "Failed to read humidity",
error.toException());
            }
        });

        return view;
    }
}

```

7.2 ESP8266 Microcontroller (Arduino IDE)

The ESP8266 microcontroller connects to the Firebase Realtime Database and controls the fan based on the database updates. It also reads temperature and humidity data from sensors and updates Firebase.

7.2.1 Firebase Setup

Include the necessary libraries for Firebase and WiFi.

```
#include <ESP8266WiFi.h>
#include <FirebaseESP8266.h>
#include <DHT.h>

// Firebase project details
#define FIREBASE_HOST "home-a598b-default-rtdb.firebaseio.com"
#define FIREBASE_AUTH "YOUR_SECURE_API_KEY"

// WiFi credentials
#define WIFI_SSID "AlKhair1 Second Floor"
#define WIFI_PASSWORD "AlkhairSecond"

// Pin to control the relay
#define RELAY_PIN D3
#define DHTPIN D4
#define DHTTYPE DHT11

DHT dht(DHTPIN, DHTTYPE);

FirebaseData firebaseData;
FirebaseConfig config;
FirebaseAuth auth;

void setup() {
  Serial.begin(115200);
  pinMode(RELAY_PIN, OUTPUT);
  digitalWrite(RELAY_PIN, LOW);
  dht.begin();

  WiFi.begin(WIFI_SSID, WIFI_PASSWORD);
  Serial.print("Connecting to WiFi");
  while (WiFi.status() != WL_CONNECTED) {
```

```

    delay(500);
    Serial.print(".");
}
Serial.println();
Serial.println("Connected to WiFi");

config.host = FIREBASE_HOST;
config.signer.tokens.legacy_token = FIREBASE_AUTH;

Firebase.begin(&config, &auth);
Firebase.reconnectWiFi(true);

if (!Firebase.beginStream(firebaseData, "/Fan")) {
    Serial.println("Error beginning stream:");
    Serial.println(firebaseData.errorReason());
} else {
    Serial.println("Stream started successfully");
}
}

void loop() {
    if (Firebase.readStream(firebaseData)) {
        if (firebaseData.streamTimeout()) {
            Serial.println("Stream timeout, reconnecting...");
            if (!Firebase.beginStream(firebaseData, "/Fan")) {
                Serial.println("Error restarting stream:");
                Serial.println(firebaseData.errorReason());
            }
            return;
        }
        if (firebaseData.dataType() == "int") {
            int relayState = firebaseData.intData();
            Serial.print("Relay State: ");
            Serial.println(relayState);
            if (relayState == 1) {
                digitalWrite(RELAY_PIN, HIGH);
                Serial.println("Relay ON");
            } else if (relayState == 0) {
                digitalWrite(RELAY_PIN, LOW);
                Serial.println("Relay OFF");
            }
        }
    }
}

```

```

    }
} else {
    if (firebaseData.httpCode() != 200) {
        Serial.print("Error code: ");
        Serial.println(firebaseData.httpCode());
        Serial.println("Failed to get data from Firebase");
        Serial.println("Reason: " + firebaseData.errorReason());
    }
}

float temperature = dht.readTemperature();
float humidity = dht.readHumidity();

if (!isnan(temperature)) {
    Firebase.setFloat(firebaseData, "/Temperature", temperature);
}
if (!isnan(humidity)) {
    Firebase.setFloat(firebaseData, "/Humidity", humidity);
}

delay(2000);
}

```